

CLASSIFICATION OF COMPOUNDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *The article presents the pragmatic analysis of compound words in modern linguistics. The specific character of new compound lexical units in correlation with their semantic intensity is reviewed.*

Key words: *Compound words, classification of compounds, word formation, derivative words, components, word stem.*

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ СЛОЖНЫХ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *В статье представлен прагматический анализ сложных слов в современной лингвистике. Рассмотрена специфика новых сложных лексических единиц в соотношении с их семантической интенсивностью.*

Ключевые слова: *сложные слова, классификация сложных слов, словообразование, производные слова, компоненты, основа слова.*

Compounds are words consisting of at least two stems which occur in the language as free forms. In a compound word the immediate constituents obtain integrity and structural cohesion that make them function in a sentence as a separate lexical unit.

The structural cohesion and integrity of a compound may depend upon unity of stress, solid or hyphenated spelling, semantic unity, unity of morphological and syntactic functioning or, more often, upon the combined effect of several of these or similar phonetic, graphic, semantic, morphological or syntactic factors.

The integrity of a compound is manifested in its indivisibility, i.e. the impossibility of inserting another word or word group between its elements. If, for example, speaking about a “sunbeam” (English) *ko`kyo`tal* we can insert some other word between the article and the noun, e.g. *a bright sunbeam*, a bright and unexpected sunbeam, because the article *a* is a separate word, no such insertion is possible between the stems *sun and beam*, *qora and ko`l*, for they are not words but morphemes.

In describing the structure of a compound one should examine three types of relations, namely the relation of the members to each other the relation of the whole to its members, and correlation with equivalent free phrases.

Some compounds are made up of a determining and a determined part, which may be called the determinant and the determinate group. Thus, a *blackboard, tomorqa* is very different from a *blackboard, tom orqa*. Its essential feature is being a teaching aid → *hovli atrofida ekin ekiladigan maydon* →: not every board of a black color is a blackboard.

A blackboard may be not a board at all but a piece of linoleum or some other suitable material. Its color is not necessarily black: it may be brown or something else. Thus, *blackboard* → a board which is black. A chatterbox – *otashqalb* is not a box, it is a person who talks a great deal without saying anything important: the combination is used only figuratively. The same metaphorical character is observed in the compound *slowcoach хомсемиз*. It is also idiomatic as it does not name a vehicle but a person who acts and thinks slowly. A *fuss – pot* is a person

easily excited and nervous about trifles. Thus for the original motivation of the idiomatic compound could be easily recreated. The following examples illustrate idiomatic compounds where it is not so obvious: “blackleg”, “strike breaker”, “blackmail” getting money or some other profit from a person by threats bluestocking “a woman affecting literary tastes and learning”

The analysis of the semantic relationship existing between the constituents of a compound presents many difficulties. Some authors have attempted a purely logical interpretation distinguishing copulative, existential, spatial and other connections. This scheme, however, failed to show the linguistic essence of compounds and was cumbersome and artificial.

Purpose of functional relations underlies such compounds as *bathrobe*, *raincoat*, *yomg`irpo`sh*, *classroom – sinfxona*, *notice – board*, and *suitcase*.

Different place or local relations are expressed in *dockland*, *garden – party*, *sea – front*. Comparison is the basis of *blockhead*, *butter – fingers*, *floodlight*, and *goldfish*. The material or elements the thing is made of is pointed out *silver wear*, *tin – hat*, *clay – pipe*. Temporal relations underlie such compounds as *night – club*, *night – duty*, *summer – house* and *day – train*. Sex – denoting compounds are rather numerous: *she – dog*, *he – goat*.

Compound words may be classified

- a) from the functional point of view;
- b) from the point of view of the way the components of the compound are linked together;
- c) from the point of view of different ways of composition.

In Uzbek the relationship between the components of compound words are different: They show:

1. Comparison: *karnaygul*, *otquloq*, *tuyaqush*, *sheryurak*, *qo`yko`z*.
2. Relevance, purposed for something: *gultuvak*, (*vase for flower*), *molqo`ra*, *olovkurak*, *tokqaychi*, *qiymataxta*. In English *washing – machine*, *blood – vessel* (a tube through which bloods flows in the body).
3. Connection to some places: *suvilon* (a snake which lives in water), *tog`olcha*, *cho`lyalpiz*, *qo`qonarava* like in English *zookeeper*, *postman*, *house keeper*, *head – dress*, *ear – ring*.
4. The mark of something: *achichiqtosh*, *olaqarg`a*, *sho`rdanak*, *qizilishton*, *Qiziltepa*. In English *long – legged*, *bluebell*, *slow – coach*.
5. Relationship to quantity: *bashbarmoq*, *mingoyoq*, *qirqog`ayni*, *Beshariq*. This rule is also relevant to English compounds such as: *three – cornered*, *fifteen – fold*, *six – fold*, *five – sided polygon*.

Uzbek compound words are classified:

- a) from the point of view of the way the components of the compound are linked together: *xomkalla*, *ko`ksulton*, *iskabtopar*.
- b) from the point of view of agreeing: *to`yboshi*, *kitobsevar*, *dunyoqarash*.
- c) from the point of view of relationship between subject and predicate: first elements of such kind compound will be predicate: *go`shkuydi*, *kelintushdi*.

In determinative compounds, however, the relationship is not attributive. For example, a foot stool is not a particular type of stool that is like a foot. Rather, it is a stool for one's foot or feet. (It can be used for sitting on but that is not its primary purpose). In a similar manner, the office manager is the manager of an office, an armchair is a chair with arms, and a raincoat is a

coat against the rain. These relationships, which are expressed by prepositions in English, would be expressed by grammatical case in other languages.

Exocentric compounds occur more often in adjectives than nouns. A barefoot girl, for example, is not a girl that is a bare foot, but a girl with a bare foot. Similarly, a V – 8 car is a car with a V – 8 engine rather than a car that is a V – 8, and a twenty – five – dollar car is a car with a worth of \$ 25, not a car that is \$ 25. The compounds shown here are bare, but more commonly, a suffixal morpheme is added, esp. – ed. Hence, a two – legged person is a person with two legs and this is exocentric.

On the other hand, endocentric adjectives are also frequently formed, using the suffixal morphemes: - ing or -er/or. A car – carrier is a clear endocentric determinative compound: it is a thing that is a carrier of cars. The related adjective, car – carrying, is also endocentric: it refers to an object which is a carrying – thing.

In the case of verb + noun compounds, the noun may be either the subject or the object of the verb. In playboy, for example, the noun is the subject of the verb (the boy plays), whereas it is the object in call girl (someone calls the girl).

A black board is any board that is black, and equal prosodic stress can be found on both elements (or, according to psycholinguist Steven Pinker, the second one is accented more heavily.) A blackboard, compound, may have started out as any other black board, but now is a thing that is constructed in a particular way, of a particular material and serves a particular purpose; the word is clearly accented on the first syllable.

Sound patterns, such as stresses placed on particular syllables, may indicate whether the word group is a compound or whether it is an adjective - + - noun phrase. A compound usually has a falling intonation: "blackboard", the "White House", as opposed to the phrases "black board". (Note that this rule does not apply in all contexts. For example, the stress pattern "white house" would be expected for the compound, which happens to be a proper name, but it is also found in the emphatic negation "No, not the black house; the white house!").

A compound adjective is a modifier of a noun. It consists of two or more morphemes of which the left – hand component limits or changes the modification of the right – hand one, as in "the dark – green dress": dark limits the green that modifies dress.

Solid compound adjectives. There are some well – established permanent compound adjectives that have become solid over a longer period, especially in American usage: earsplitting, eye catching. However, in British usage these, apart from downtown, are more likely written with a hyphen: ear – splitting.

There are a group of words which form compound adjectives, such as: aralash, yo`q, ko`l, oliy, och, to`q, to`la, chala: *qumaralash loy, tengi yo`q qiz, ko`p tarmoqli soha, oliy ma`lumotli, och qizil, qorni to`q, to`q qizil.*

In English we can also find the signal words which form compound adjectives; but they are hyphenated: light, dark, long, middle, high: e.g. light – green, dark-blue, middle-aged, long-legged, and high-qualified.

Therefore, some of the above definitions cannot fully express the concept of a compound word. In addition, the idea that complex words consist of components with independent meanings cannot be applied to complex words in the Uzbek language. This is due to the fact that one or all components of double and repeated words in Uzbek, such as nest-nobud, meva-cheva,

apak-chapak, as well as compound words such as hardamkhayol, harkim, sharsharak, consist of elements or metaphors that cannot be used independently.

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